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Wide spectral range optical characterization of terbium gallium garnet (TGG) single crystal by universal dispersion model

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ABSTRACT

Terbium gallium garnet (TGG – $\text{Tb}_3\text{Ga}_5\text{O}_{12}$) single crystal was optically characterized using the multi-sample and multi-instrument method across a wide spectral range with the help of the universal dispersion model. The obtained optical constants cover the spectral range from the far-IR region (25 cm^{-1}) to the vacuum-UV region (10.3 eV). The applied dispersion model includes all elementary absorption processes occurring within the spectral range that affect the dielectric response, including phonons and valence electron excitations. The primary objective was to accurately determine the optical constants with the highest possible precision. The optical results were compared with *ab initio* density functional theory calculations to gain insight into the nature of the absorption edge and the distribution of the f-electron excitations.

1. Introduction

The utilization of high-average power lasers is becoming increasingly prevalent in a multitude of scientific and industrial applications, including laser processing, generation of intense UV light, inertial fusion, and as pump lasers for high-repetition femtosecond petawatt laser systems [1–9].

In the context of laser technology, Faraday isolators play a pivotal role in suppressing back-reflections and preventing damage to the laser cavity. Some magneto-optical materials utilized in Faraday isolators include YIG, TIG, CeF_3 , KTF, TSAG, and Dy_2O_3 [10–12]. Terbium gallium garnet (TGG – $\text{Tb}_3\text{Ga}_5\text{O}_{12}$) is a well-known magneto-optical material that exhibits strong Faraday rotation, making it a promising candidate for use in Faraday isolators for laser systems [13–15]. However, the performance of Faraday isolators heavily depends on the spectral range of operation, and the use of TGG has traditionally been constrained to a relatively narrow range within the visible and near-infrared regions.

The requirements for a Faraday rotation element include a high Verdet constant, size scalability, excellent optical quality, high laser-induced-damage threshold, and high thermal strength [16]. Tb-doped phosphate and silicate glasses have often been used in large-diameter glass laser systems [17,18] due to superior size scalability, but these amorphous materials are unsuitable for high-average power lasers due to their low thermal conductivity. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in extending the spectral range of TGG-based optical

isolators into the near-IR region [19], which is crucial for applications such as sensing, spectroscopy, and free-space communications.

In addition to civilian applications, the new multi-kW laser directed-energy effectors introduced by governmental bodies are expected to utilize these magneto-optical materials [20,21]. More recent developments have focused on the potential of wireless power transmission from space to Earth [22]. In this context, laser beams could be employed to transport power generated in space down to Earth.

Accurate modeling of material response functions is a necessary step from both purely theoretical and practical perspectives. From a theoretical standpoint, a complex wide-spectral-range optical characterization of the material is a valuable tool for a deeper understanding of excitation processes. This article will present the motivation for performing such a characterization.

From the practical point of view, precise characterization enables the reliable determination of the optical constants of TGG in the transparent region at wavelengths where the material is used in practice. The determination of the weak extinction coefficient subsequently affects the applicability of this material. Moreover, this will facilitate precise optical characterization over a broad spectral range of layered systems deposited on TGG crystals, such as anti-reflective (AR) coatings. It is exceedingly challenging to characterize these coatings in the spectral region where the system exhibits poor reflectivity.

The precise determination of optical constants is achievable through the combination of spectroscopic ellipsometry and spectrophotometry

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Table 1

List of the experimental data with spectral ranges (including resolution) and angle of incidence (AOI). The fitted experimental data R , T , and I_s, I_c, I_n represent the reflectance, transmittance, and associated ellipsometric quantities [29], respectively.

Data set number	Instrument	Quantity	Samples	Range, AOI	Resolution	Figures
1, 2, 3	Woollam IR-VASE	I_s, I_c, I_n	#1, #2, #3	250–5700 cm^{-1} , 55–75°	1 cm^{-1}	7
4, 5, 6	Horiba Jobin Yvon UVISEL	I_s, I_c, I_n	#1, #2, #3	0.6–6.5 eV, 55–75°	2 nm	17
7, 8, 9	Bruker Vertex 70v	R	#1, #2, #3	25–680 cm^{-1} , 10°	1 cm^{-1}	5, 7
10, 11	Bruker Vertex 70v	T	#2, #3	25–680 cm^{-1} , 0°	1 cm^{-1}	5
12, 13, 14	Bruker Vertex 80v	R	#1, #2, #3	370–7500 cm^{-1} , 10°	8 cm^{-1}	7
15, 16, 17	Bruker Vertex 80v	T	#1, #2, #3	1000–7500 cm^{-1} , 0°	8 cm^{-1}	9, 10, 11
18, 19, 20	Perkin Elmer Lambda 1050+	T	#1, #2, #3	860–2500 nm, 0°	5 nm	10, 11
21, 22, 23	Perkin Elmer Lambda 1050+	R	#1, #2, #3	280–880 nm, 6°	0.25 nm	16
24, 25, 26	Perkin Elmer Lambda 1050+	T	#1, #2, #3	280–880 nm, 0°	0.25 nm	
27, 28, 29	Perkin Elmer Lambda 1050+	R	#1, #2, #3	190–319 nm, 6°	1 nm	16, 17
30, 31, 32	Perkin Elmer Lambda 1050+	T	#1, #2, #3	465–510 nm, 0°	0.05 nm	12
33, 34, 35	Perkin Elmer Lambda 1050+	T	#1, #2, #3	280–400 nm, 0°	0.05 nm	13, 15, 16
36	McPherson VUVAS 1000	R	#3	120–318 nm, 10°	1 nm	17

Fig. 1. Photo of TGG crystals used for optical characterization.

over a wide spectral range. In order to describe optical constants, the universal dispersion model is employed, which is capable of efficiently, accurately, and physically correctly describing the response functions over a wide spectral range [23]. TGG is the third cubic crystalline structure material to be thoroughly investigated using this dispersion model. In the past, crystalline silicon [24] and yttrium aluminum garnet (YAG – $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$) crystals [25] have been studied. Consequently, this article will compare the response functions over a wide spectral range with those materials.

Ab initio calculations can provide a robust theoretical framework for investigating the electronic structure of condensed matter, particularly crystals [26]. In addition to providing comprehensive insight into the electronic structure, *ab initio* calculations can assist in the comprehension of excited states and the explanation of the optical properties of materials, thereby facilitating advanced optical characterization. Although these calculations provide valuable theoretical insights, they rely on approximations and assumptions that can lead to discrepancies when compared to actual optical spectra. Indeed, the most prevalent *ab initio* method, density functional theory (DFT), is a ground-state theory and while more sophisticated and rigorous approaches, like the GW method [27], BSE [28] or TD-DFT are available, they are much more computationally demanding, rendering their application to complex magneto-optical systems with highly correlated electrons such as TGG challenging. These issues will be extensively discussed in the article.

2. Experimental data and data processing

Three distinct, dual-side polished TGG commercial samples were utilized in this research (Fig. 1): #1 $20 \times 20 \times 5$ mm square plate (Onyx Optics, USA), #2 30×3 mm disk (Nanjing Metalaser Photonics, China), and #3 $10 \times 10 \times 0.5$ mm square plate (MSE Supplies, USA). All crystals were laser-grade polished and exhibited (111) orientation.

In this paper, the results of optical characterization are based on the simultaneous processing of experimental data measured across a wide spectral range. This was achieved by utilizing four spectrophotometers (Bruker Vertex 70v, Bruker Vertex 80v, Perkin Elmer Lambda 1050+, McPherson VUVAS 1000) and two variable angle spectroscopic

ellipsometers (Woollam IR-VASE, Horiba Jobin Yvon UVISEL). As in a previous article [25], a similar heterogeneous data set was used for each TGG sample. A special high-resolution transmittance measurement was performed in the visible and UV regions covering the spectral region of f-electron excitations (Perkin Elmer Lambda 1050+: regions 280–400 nm and 465–510 nm, step and resolution 0.05 nm). A total of 36 distinct experimental spectroscopic measurements (reflectances, transmittances and ellipsometric quantities) were included in the presented optical characterization (see Table 1).

Furthermore, our experimental spectroscopic data are supplemented by the tabulated refractive index values provided by Schlarb and Sugg in [30]. Data processing was carried out using newAD2 open-source software [31], which employs a modified Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm, as previously described in our publication [25]. The algorithm is of crucial importance, as it enables the efficient fitting of a set of heterogeneous data by automatically determining the data weights corresponding to individual measurements on different instruments and samples, in conjunction with the tabulated data.

Note that TGG has a cubic body-centered structure with 80 atoms in the primitive cell, space group $\text{Ia}\bar{3}\text{m}$, int. n. 230, point group $\text{m}\bar{3}\text{m}$ [32] (Materials Project id: mp-5965). Therefore, the linear dielectric response can be modeled to a first approximation by an isotropic dielectric function. Optical activity, whether natural or induced by a magnetic field, was not modeled in this study.

3. Universal dispersion model

A dielectric response function of TGG has been described using a universal dispersion model (UDM) [23]. The optical constants determined by the UDM satisfy three fundamental conditions, *i.e.*, time reversal symmetry, Kramers–Kronig (KK) consistency and conformity with sum rules. This is of significant importance for optical characterization in the wide spectral range from far-IR to the vacuum-UV region. The model was originally developed for the description of disordered (amorphous and polycrystalline) materials forming thin films. However, it can be extended to crystalline materials using various modifications. The model has been already applied to crystalline silicon (c-Si) and yttrium aluminum garnet (YAG) crystals in our previous works [24,25]. Individual excitations (contributions to the overall response function) are modeled using individual elementary dispersion models, which must be selected within the framework of the UDM.

Conventional approaches to the distribution of optical constants are either tabular or based on the Sellmeier formula, which is applicable only in the region of transparency. The current state of the UDM implementation, which can be found in the newAD2 software [31], describes optical response of any condensed matter systems (amorphous, polycrystalline, single crystals, *etc.*). In the newAD2 software, the UDM defined by dispersion parameters serves as a substitute for tabulated optical constants. Note that the implementation of UDM

Fig. 2. Modeled complex dielectric functions ϵ for crystalline materials (TGG, YAG and c-Si) in both real ϵ_r and imaginary ϵ_i parts. Bottom panel shows the corresponding transition strength functions ($F(E) = E\epsilon_i(E)$).

includes attributes that determine the usage of elementary dispersion models describing specific absorption processes within the medium.

The comparison of the dielectric response function in a wide spectral range for c-Si and YAG crystals with the response function determined in this article for TGG is shown in Fig. 2. The following text outlines the specific contributions employed for the TGG modeling and highlights the differences in approach compared to the models for c-Si and YAG.

Note that the hat symbol above the function or quantity designation is used in our nomenclature to denote complex quantities, while the real and imaginary parts are denoted with subscripts “r” and “i”.

3.1. Phonon absorption

The best approach for describing IR-active transverse optical (TO) phonons in UDM is to employ an asymmetric peak approximation model with a Voigt distribution function [23–25]. In this model, each vibrational mode is represented in the imaginary part of response function by a Voigt profile with a complex amplitude and the j -th phonon absorption peak is described by five parameters: the excitation energy $E_{ph,j}$, the transition strength of the symmetric part of the peak $N_{ph,j}$, the transition strength of the asymmetric part of the peak $M_{ph,j}$, the full width at half maximum (FWHM) $B_{ph,j}$ and the ratio of the Lorentzian component in the Voigt profile $L_{ph,j}$. The complex Voigt profile can be efficiently calculated using the complex Faddeeva function [33,34], which is defined by the following integral:

$$\hat{W}(\hat{z}) = \frac{i}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\exp(-t^2)}{\hat{z} - t} dt. \quad (1)$$

The contribution to the response function $\hat{\chi}_{ph,j}(E)$ (complex susceptibility dependent on photon energy) can be expressed using two complex Faddeeva functions, as shown below:

$$\hat{\chi}_{ph,j}(E) = \frac{iN_{ph,j}E_{ph,j} - M_{ph,j}E}{C_N \sqrt{2\pi} E_{ph,j}^2 \sigma_{ph,j}} \left[\hat{W} \left(\frac{E - E_{ph,j} + i\gamma_{ph,j}/2}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_{ph,j}} \right) \right]$$

$$- \hat{W} \left(\frac{E + E_{ph,j} + i\gamma_{ph,j}/2}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_{ph,j}} \right), \quad (2)$$

where $\gamma_{ph,j}$ is FWHM of Lorentzian part of Voigt profile, *i. e.*,

$$\gamma_{ph,j} = L_{ph,j} B_{ph,j}, \quad (3)$$

and $\sigma_{ph,j}$ is root mean square (RMS) value of Gaussian part of Voigt profile, *i. e.*,

$$\sigma_{ph,j} = \frac{B_{ph,j}}{2\sqrt{2\ln 2}} \sqrt{(1 - aL_{ph,j})^2 - (1 - a)^2 L_{ph,j}^2}, \quad (4)$$

where $a = 0.5346$ (the two aforementioned equations provide an approximation of the relations between the broadening parameters and $L_{ph,j}$ with sufficient accuracy). The symbol C_N denotes the normalization constant that is shared among all phonon excitations described below.

The model of a single asymmetric peak is not consistent with sum rules. Specifically, the model exhibits incorrect asymptotic behavior, and the f -sum rule integral, which is proportional to the density of charged particles in the studied system, diverges, *i. e.*,

$$\int_0^{\infty} E \chi_{i,ph,j}(E) dE = \pm\infty, \quad (5)$$

where $\chi_{i,ph,j}(E)$ is the imaginary part of j -th phonon contribution to the dielectric function (susceptibility). The sign of the integral depends on the sign of the transition strength $M_{ph,j}$. This deficiency can be remedied by incorporating multiple asymmetric peaks and imposing constraints on the parameters $M_{ph,j}$ describing the asymmetric parts of the peaks. This guarantees that the summation integral describing the response function of all peaks is finite:

$$\sum_{j=1}^m \frac{M_{ph,j}}{E_{ph,j}} = 0. \quad (6)$$

The total number of free parameters describing phonon excitations is $(5m - 1)$, where m represents the number of vibrational modes

(phonons), since the parameter $M_{\text{ph},1}$ is determined by the constraint. The total transition strength is then calculated from imaginary part of phonon contributions to the dielectric function as follows:

$$N_{\text{ph}} = \sum_{j=1}^m \int_0^{\infty} E \chi_{i,\text{ph},j}(E) dE = \sum_{j=1}^m N_{\text{ph},j}, \quad (7)$$

where the summation is performed over all phonons in the system. This sum rule integral defines the normalization constant C_N :

$$C_N = N_{\text{ph}}^{-1} \sum_{j=1}^m \left(N_{\text{ph},j} + \frac{M_{\text{ph},j} \gamma_{\text{ph},j}}{E_{\text{ph},j}} \right). \quad (8)$$

As illustrated in Fig. 2, phonon excitations of YAG and TGG crystals are observed for energies below approximately 0.1 eV (wavelengths greater than 10 μm). Both garnet crystals have a cubic body-centered structure with 80 atoms in the primitive cell, space group $Ia\bar{3}m$, int. n. 230, point group $m\bar{3}m$, Wyckoff positions 16a Al/Ga, 24c Y/Tb, 24d Al/Ga, and 96 h O [32] (mp-3050 and mp-5965). The Wyckoff positions of the atoms correspond to 3, 3, 3 and 9 dielectric-active vibrational modes, which lead to a total of 17 IR-active TO phonons after subtracting one mode corresponding to the acoustic branch [35,36]. Given the identical garnet structure, it can be assumed that the phonon dispersion models describing the response functions of YAG and TGG crystals may be completely identical.

Of course, as can be seen from Fig. 2 the position, strength and shape of the absorption peaks differ due to the different masses of the cations in TGG (Tb^{+3} , Ga^{+3}) compared to those in YAG crystals (Y^{+3} , Al^{+3}). As will be demonstrated in the experimental section later, TGG has a somewhat more complicated shape of the TO phonon absorption peaks. This difference arises because Ga atoms exist in two different isotopes, unlike the other atoms in TGG and YAG crystals.

For illustration, the response function of c-Si shows no TO phonon excitations due to its homopolar cubic crystal structure with a diamond lattice (space group $Fd\bar{3}m$, int. n. 227, point group $m\bar{3}m$). These crystals contain two atoms in the primitive cell and one IR-inactive TO phonon, which can only appear as a very weak absorption peak in the spectra due to translational symmetry breaking. In comparison to typical IR-active phonon peaks, its transition strength is approximately six orders of magnitude smaller. The weak absorption band observed between 0.05 and 0.2 eV is primarily due to multi-phonon absorption processes and, to some extent, to absorption features induced by impurities in c-Si. Previous work [23] demonstrated that this absorption band can be described using discrete asymmetric peaks. However, a more physically accurate model based on Gaussian-broadened continuous bands was also presented [37–39]. Absorption below 0.05 eV was attributed to free carriers, since the silicon was lightly doped with boron [24].

It should be noted that multi-phonon absorption is also observed in TGG and YAG crystals. Since the transition strength is three to four orders of magnitude lower than that of TO phonons, detecting these absorption effects is challenging. For TGG and YAG crystals approximately 1 mm thick, the absorption edge is located in the spectral region where two-phonon absorption ends, *i. e.*, approximately at twice the maximum frequency of TO phonons. In this region, multi-phonon absorptive structures can be effectively modeled using Gaussian broadened symmetric peaks ($M_{\text{ph},j} = L_{\text{ph},j} = 0$). Therefore, within the TO phonon model, multiple peaks must be used for modeling multi-phonon absorption as needed.

3.2. Valence electron excitations

In terms of interband electronic excitations around the absorption edge, the crystalline materials can be classified into two groups: materials with indirect and direct band gaps. In materials with an indirect band gap, the fundamental absorption edge is formed by indirect transitions, where the excitation of an electron from the valence to the conduction band occurs simultaneously with the excitation or annihilation of a phonon. In these materials, direct interband transitions

are observed at higher energies against the background of direct transitions. Crystalline silicon is a prototypical example of materials with an indirect band gap. Using on a relatively sophisticated dispersion model, the total strength of indirect transitions in c-Si at room temperature was determined to be about seven times weaker than that of direct transitions [39].

The absorption edge exhibits, similarly to disordered materials, a quadratic increase in absorbance, allowing the use of dispersion models with an absorption edge based on the so-called Tauc dependence [40–44]

$$\varepsilon_i(E) \propto \frac{(E - E_g)^2}{E^2} \Theta(E - E_g), \quad (9)$$

where Θ is the Heaviside step function. For crystalline materials, it is necessary to split the absorption edge into two branches that describe the electron excitation processes with simultaneous phonon excitation and simultaneous phonon annihilation [23,24,45,46].

For crystalline materials with a direct band gap, the absorption edge is much steeper. In a proper model, both direct and indirect transitions must be taken into account. However, only direct transitions are responsible for the steep increase in absorption at the band gap. For direct transitions, the following relationship for the absorption edge is often expected (see *e. g.*, [12,47])

$$\varepsilon_i(E) \propto \frac{\sqrt{E - E_g}}{E^2} \Theta(E - E_g). \quad (10)$$

Nevertheless, the absorption edge given exactly by (10) is not observed experimentally. Eq. (10) is derived from three assumptions. Firstly, it is necessary to assume that electrons behave as independent particles, which is known as the single-particle approximation. Secondly, the direct transition occurs between parabolic isotropic bands (it is a direct transition at the Γ point). Third, a constant matrix element is assumed.

While the second and third assumptions can be met for certain materials, the first assumption is usually not fulfilled because electrons and holes (excitons) are strongly interacting quasi-particles. It is therefore necessary to take this effect into account. The experimentally observed absorption edge is in relatively good agreement with Elliott's model of 3D Wannier excitons [48], *i. e.*, excitons with delocalized electron states. The Elliott model predicts the following imaginary part of the response function:

$$\varepsilon_i(E) \propto \frac{1}{E^2} \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2R}{n^3} \delta\left(E - E_g + \frac{R}{n^2}\right) + \frac{\Theta(E - E_g)}{1 - \exp\left(-2\pi\sqrt{\frac{R}{E - E_g}}\right)} \right], \quad (11)$$

where R is binding energy of the lowest exciton ($n = 1$). Note that Eq. (11) has limit in (10) when R approaches zero:

$$\lim_{R \rightarrow 0} \frac{2\pi\sqrt{R}}{1 - \exp\left(-2\pi\sqrt{\frac{R}{X}}\right)} = \sqrt{X}. \quad (12)$$

As outlined in (11), Elliott's model is not applicable within the universal dispersion model because it leads to an infinite sum rule integral. To ensure the finiteness of the sum rule integral, it is necessary to truncate the joint density of states corresponding to this model for the energy E_1 , which corresponds to the energy of the selected critical point M_1 . Nevertheless, it is essential to broaden this function and express the real part using KK integration, thereby enabling the model to be utilized in practice.

In our advanced model of c-Si, piecewise-smooth functions are utilized to describe the joint density of states between critical points (van Hove singularities [49]), which are then broadened using a Gaussian function. Further details can be found in earlier works [23,39,50,51]. This advanced dispersion model is equivalent in terms of Gaussian broadening to the parametric optical model proposed by Herzinger and Johs et al. [52,53]. However, our model is parametrized differently,

which allows us to effectively model the temperature dependence of the response function.

Another possibility for parametrizing interband electron excitations is to use the Lorentz distribution function for the broadening van Hove singularities. This approach was introduced by Adachi [54–56] and applied by Tanguy to Elliott's model [57]. The advantage of broadening with the Lorentz function is that it leads to a closed analytical form. However, the Lorentzian distribution is not very suitable for modeling electron excitations because the broadened function decreases too slowly, making it difficult to precisely model the region below the fundamental absorption edge.

Since the application of Gaussian broadening must be solved numerically or with the help of special functions that allow Gaussian broadening of a polynomial function [23,58], Kim et al. [59] proposed introducing the spectral dependence of the Lorentzian broadening parameter in the response function. If a Gaussian function is chosen as the dependence function of the Lorentzian broadening parameter, a dispersion model that closely approximates the model with Gaussian broadening is achieved. Djurišić et al. applied this approach to Elliott's model [60].

However, c-Si has a relatively simple electronic band structure, as it has only four valence electrons. In contrast, crystalline materials like TGG contain a greater number of electrons in their valence bands. It is therefore appropriate to model the dielectric response using simpler models, at least in the initial stage of studying an unknown material. This article demonstrates that dispersion models combining truncated Lorentzian functions with Gaussian peaks can accurately describe the response function of interband electron excitations in crystalline materials. Similar models have been used previously for c-Si and YAG crystals [24,25].

The following form of excitonic contributions was used to model crystalline TGG:

$$\chi_{i,ex,k}(E) = \frac{N_{Gex,k}}{\sqrt{\pi}E_{ex,k}B_{ex,k}} \left[\exp\left(-\frac{(E-E_{ex,k})^2}{B_{ex,k}^2}\right) - \exp\left(-\frac{(E+E_{ex,k})^2}{B_{ex,k}^2}\right) \right] + \frac{N_{Lex,k}}{C_{N,k}} \frac{(|E| - E_g)^2}{\left[(|E| - E_{ex,k})^2 + B_{ex,k}^2/4 \right] E^3} \Theta(|E| - E_g), \quad (13)$$

where the first part represents Gaussian contribution and the second part, which is accompanied by a Heaviside step function, denotes truncated Lorentzian term. In this context, the index k denotes individual excitons. The real part of Lorentzian term is expressed using KK integration of rational function [44]. The real part of Gaussian term is expressed with help of Dawson function (integral) [23,33,61,62]. The dispersion parameters are as follows: $N_{Gex,k}$ transition strength of Gaussian part; $N_{Lex,k}$ transition strength of truncated Lorentzian part; $E_{ex,k}$ peak position; $B_{ex,k}$ broadening parameter; E_g band gap parameter which is common for the all excitonic contributions. The truncated Lorentzian part is divided by a normalization constant $C_{N,k}$ to satisfy the following sum rule

$$\int_0^\infty E \chi_{i,ex,k}(E) dE = N_{Gex,k} + N_{Lex,k}. \quad (14)$$

The expression for the normalization constant and the real part of the response function can be found in previous work [44]. In three-dimensional crystalline materials, excitons are situated at critical points M_0 and anisotropic points M_1 [46]. The index k distinguishes individual excitons in the model but may also index weak features unrelated to excitons, resulting from structures in the joint density of states. Therefore, it is necessary to approach the concept of an excitonic contribution (13) with the utmost caution.

To accurately model the absorption band over a wide spectral range, it is advisable to introduce broad-band contributions into the model.

The following three-parameter contribution can be used:

$$\chi_{i,bb}(E) = \frac{N_{bb} (|E| - E_g)^2}{C_{Nbb} \left[(|E| - E_g)^2 + \frac{(E_{bb} - E_g)^3}{E_g} \right] E^3} \Theta(|E| - E_g), \quad (15)$$

where E_g is the common band gap parameter, E_{bb} is energy where the transition strength function $E \chi_{i,bb}(E)$ attains a maximum, N_{bb} is the transition strength parameter, and C_{Nbb} is the normalization constant dependent on the dispersion parameters, ensuring that the sum rule integral equals N_{bb} . The calculation of the normalization constant and the real part of the response function is provided in Appendix A.

3.3. Excitation of f-electrons

Terbium atoms have two s and nine f valence electrons, while gallium atoms have two s and one p valence electrons. Each terbium and gallium atom donates three electrons to oxygen atoms, behaving as Tb^{+3} and Ga^{+3} cations in TGG. Oxygen behaves in TGG as an O^{-2} anion with a full shell of six p electrons forming the valence band of delocalized electrons with large energy dispersion. The remaining eight f-electrons in TGG behave in a manner analogous to those in an isolated Tb^{+3} cation, meaning that they are localized and form narrow bands below the Fermi energy. These f-electrons can then be excited to narrow bands above the Fermi energy, which arise from the unoccupied six f orbitals of the Tb^{+3} cation.

Excitations of f-electrons are manifested by narrow, very weak structures in the region where TGG exhibits transparency (above multiphonon excitations and below the band gap of valence extended electronic states). A comprehensive analysis of the excitations of f-electrons in TGG was conducted in the article by Gruber et al. [63]. The f-electron states are described using three quantum numbers as $|L, S, J\rangle$, where the numbers are the total orbital momentum, the total spin number, and total angular momentum, respectively. For Tb^{3+} cation, this numbers are all positive integers [64]:

$$S = 0, 1, 2, 3, \quad L = 0, 1, \dots, 12, \quad L + S \leq 12, \quad (16)$$

$$J = |L - S|, \dots, L + S,$$

resulting in 154 individual states. This relatively low number of excited states corresponds to inviolate states without accounting for the Stark and Zeeman effects.

Table 2 shows the standard designations $^{2S+1}L_J$ of the ground and selected excited states of the f-electrons as used in emission and absorption spectroscopy [64,65]. Instead of the value of L , the following series of capital letters is used in this designation:

$$L = S, P, D, F, G, H, I, K, L, M, N, O, Q, \quad (17)$$

similar to the designation of the orbital moment of single-electron states where series s, p, d, f, g, \dots is used. In Table 2, the total angular momentum of f-electrons is calculated as follows

$$J = \sum_k s_{z,k} + l_{z,k}, \quad (18)$$

where $s_{z,k}$ and $l_{z,k}$ are the projections of the spin number and the orbital momentum of individual f-electrons to resulting total angular momentum.

It should be noted that considering f-electrons in terms of single-electron states is somewhat misleading. The total number of combinations of 8 electrons occupying 14 single-electron states is 3003. A significant number of these states are equivalent because the energies of the single-electron states change with electron configuration. Additionally, the states corresponding to individual columns of the table are written in a different basis (the z direction changes with the resulting vector J). The energy of these individual states depends on the excitation state, so it is more appropriate to assign energy to the overall state $^{2S+1}L_J$. A considerable amount of states are absent from Table 2. For example states 5F_5 , 5H_7 , 5I_8 , and 5K_9 , which correspond

Table 2

Classification of f-electron states of Tb³⁺ cation used in emission and absorption spectroscopy which were identified by Gruber et al. [63] in absorption spectra of TGG. The single-electron states can be distinguished by two quantum numbers: projection of the electron orbital momentum l_z and spin s_z to direction of total angular momentum vector J . The symbols \bullet and \circ represent the occupied and respectively unoccupied states. Dashed line symbolizes the Fermi energy.

$ l_z, s_z\rangle$	7F_6	7F_5	7F_4	7F_3	7F_2	7F_1	7F_0	5D_4	5D_3	5G_6	$^5L_{10}$	5G_3	5D_2	5G_4	5L_9
$ -3, \downarrow\rangle$	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\bullet	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ
$ -2, \downarrow\rangle$	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\bullet	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ
$ -1, \downarrow\rangle$	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\bullet	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ
$ 0, \downarrow\rangle$	\circ	\circ	\circ	\bullet	\circ	\circ	\bullet	\bullet	\circ						
$ +1, \downarrow\rangle$	\circ	\circ	\bullet	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\bullet	\circ	\circ	\bullet	\circ	\circ	\bullet
$ +2, \downarrow\rangle$	\circ	\bullet	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\bullet	\circ	\bullet	\bullet	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ
$ +3, \downarrow\rangle$	\bullet	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet
$ +3, \uparrow\rangle$	\bullet	\circ	\circ	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet	\circ	\bullet	\bullet						
$ +2, \uparrow\rangle$	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet										
$ +1, \uparrow\rangle$	\bullet	\circ	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet	\circ	\bullet								
$ 0, \uparrow\rangle$	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet										
$ -1, \uparrow\rangle$	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet										
$ -2, \uparrow\rangle$	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet										
$ -3, \uparrow\rangle$	\bullet	\circ	\bullet	\bullet	\bullet	\circ									

to single-electron transitions from occupied states $|+2, \uparrow\rangle$, $|0, \uparrow\rangle$, $|-1, \uparrow\rangle$, and $|-2, \uparrow\rangle$ to the unoccupied state $|+2, \downarrow\rangle$ are not included in table because they were not identified in the IR spectra by Gruber et al. [63]. Ultimately, it is not possible to reach a multitude of excited states merely by exciting a single electron from the ground state. The single-electron description is not suitable for these excitations, as changes in the energy of these excited states can lead to confusion in interpretation. However, this is not a major concern, as multi-electron excitations are less probable and are not observed in absorption spectra. The purpose of creating Table 2 is to enable a comparison of excited states of f-electrons with DFT calculations that use a band structure scheme where individual single-electron states can be identified (see Section 5.6).

Compared to other electron excitations, the weak transition strength of f-electron excitations from occupied to unoccupied f states can be attributed to the low probability of these transitions, which are forbidden by the selection rules for an isolated Tb³⁺ cation. These structures can be effectively modeled by a discrete absorption spectrum with a Gaussian profile. Due to the static electric field in the ionic crystals, the f-electron levels are split (Stark effect), resulting in the absorption bands having a complex structure [12,63,64,66].

The aim of this article is not to provide a detailed account of the aforementioned absorption structure. The objective of this study is to provide a comprehensive and accurate description of the optical response within this region. Accordingly, a dispersive model based on discrete excitations was used, described by three parameters: transition strength $N_{fe,l}$, position in the spectrum $E_{fe,l}$, and FWHM $B_{fe,l}$:

$$\chi_{i,fe,l}(E) = \frac{2\sqrt{\ln 2} N_{fe,l}}{\sqrt{\pi} E_{fe,l} B_{fe,l}} \left[\exp\left(-4 \ln 2 \frac{(E - E_{fe,l})^2}{B_{fe,l}^2}\right) - \exp\left(-4 \ln 2 \frac{(E + E_{fe,l})^2}{B_{fe,l}^2}\right) \right], \quad (19)$$

where index l corresponds to individual Stark levels. The real part is expressed using KK integration with the help of the Dawson function (integral) [23,33,61,62].

3.4. Excitation involving localized states

Localized states of electrons observed in nearly perfect crystals are determined by various lattice defects, *i.e.*, when local translational symmetry is missing in the lattice for some reason. In terms of electron excitations involving localized states, two phenomena can be observed in absorption spectra: exponential tails near the fundamental absorption edge and very weak, relatively broad absorption peaks within the band of forbidden energies.

The contribution of the exponential tail to the response function is modeled differently for energies smaller than and larger than the band gap energy E_g :

$$\chi_{i,et}(E) = \frac{N_{et}}{E} F_e^0(E), \quad E \in [0, E_g], \quad (20)$$

$$\chi_{i,et}(E) = \frac{N_{et}}{E} F_r^0(E), \quad E \in (E_g, \infty), \quad (21)$$

where N_{et} denotes transition strength. The normalized transition strength function is modeled separately using exponential part

$$F_e^0(E) = A_e \left[\cosh\left(\frac{E}{E_u}\right) - 1 \right], \quad (22)$$

and rational part

$$F_r^0(E) = A_r \frac{(|E| - E_x)^2}{E^4}. \quad (23)$$

The symbols A_e , A_r , and E_x are internal parameters of the model chosen such that the following normalization sum rule integral holds

$$\int_0^{E_g} F_e^0(E) dE + \int_{E_g}^{\infty} F_r^0(E) dE = 1, \quad (24)$$

and the response function is smooth at the point E_g up to its first derivative:

$$F_e^0(E_g) = F_r^0(E_g), \quad \left. \frac{dF_e^0(E)}{dE} = \frac{dF_r^0(E)}{dE} \right|_{E=E_g}. \quad (25)$$

For purposes of reference, the complete model definition is provided in Appendix B.

Wide absorption peaks representing excitations of electrons from occupied localized states to unoccupied localized states are modeled using Gaussian peaks. In this instance, however, the parameter $B_{loc,s}$ represents the root mean square (RMS) value of the peak width:

$$\chi_{i,lok,s}(E) = \frac{N_{loc,s}}{\sqrt{2\pi} E_{loc,s} B_{loc,s}} \left[\exp\left(-\frac{(E - E_{loc,s})^2}{2B_{loc,s}^2}\right) - \exp\left(-\frac{(E + E_{loc,s})^2}{2B_{loc,s}^2}\right) \right], \quad (26)$$

where the remaining two dispersion parameters $E_{loc,s}$ and $N_{loc,s}$ indicate the position and transition strength of these excitations.

4. Ab initio calculations

The electron band structure of TGG was modeled using the density functional theory (DFT) [67,68], as implemented in the all-electron full-potential plane-wave Wien2k package [69]. The standard generalized gradient approximation (GGA) by Perdew, Burke, and Ernzerhof

(PBE) [70] was employed for the description of exchange and correlation effects, however, an onsite hybrid potential [71] was used to improve the description of strongly correlated Tb 4f states, which are difficult to properly describe with plain GGA. Spin polarization was included and a ferromagnetic configuration was considered. We note that this approximation is the main shortcoming of our model. In fact, a quite complex non-collinear structure of the magnetic moments was reported for TGG [72,73], however, it is not possible to model within the constraints of collinear DFT. Initial TGG structure as reported by Materials Project was fully relaxed with respect to cell size and atomic positions, such that the residual forces were lower than $0.01 \text{ eV}/\text{\AA}$. Numerical precision parameters included a k -point grid of $5 \times 5 \times 5$, a basis set size parameter $R_{\text{mt}} K_{\text{max}}$ of 8.0, with the corresponding muffin tin radii being 2.1, 1.8, and 1.6 Bohr radii for Tb, Ga, and O, respectively, and a plane-wave expansion cutoff G_{max} of 20 Bohr radii $^{-1}$. All *ab initio* calculations can be accessed in the NOMAD Archive under the Creative Commons license [74,75].

5. Results and discussion

5.1. Dispersion of refractive index in the region of transparency

Optical techniques such as variable-angle spectroscopic ellipsometry or spectrophotometry at a normal or near-normal angle of incidence are not sufficient for the precise determination of the refractive index in the region of transparency. The most suitable method for determining the refractive index of the bulk materials is the minimum deviation method (MDM) [76]. In order to conduct MDM measurements, it is essential to use a triangular-shaped prism made from the material needed to be investigated. If such a prism is not available, often due to the manufacturing complexity, or the unavailability of the MDM setup, it is advisable to obtain refractive index data from a reliable source where MDM method was used in combination with other techniques. In this case, the data were obtained through spectroscopic optical measurements using a heterogeneous data processing algorithm. This latter method was successfully used for the optical characterization of float-zone c-Si [24] and pure YAG crystal [25].

Finding relevant data measured using the MDM method was particularly difficult for TGG. However, alternative methods with greater accuracy in refractive index determination than the spectroscopic approach are available. The most relevant refractive index values appear to be those published by Schlarb and Sugg [30], considering the refractive indices published so far by various authors using different experimental methods [30,77–79]. A detailed analysis and justification of the chosen refractive indices are provided in Appendix C.

The refractive index n of TGG, as tabulated by Schlarb and Sugg [30] and including uncertainty intervals, is shown in Fig. 3. Moreover, the figure also depicts the spectral dependencies of the refractive index obtained in this study. The final fit is based on the combined processing of our experimental data and the tabulated refractive index. For comparison, an alternative fit is also presented, in which the tabulated refractive index was omitted during the processing of the experimental data.

In Fig. 4, a detailed view of the refractive index in the near-IR region is shown, which is the region in which TGG crystals are primarily used. It is evident that the refractive index determined from both fits lies within the uncertainty interval of the tabulated data. Nevertheless, in the near-IR region, the refractive index from alternative fit is positioned at the lower end of the aforementioned uncertainty interval.

The statistical uncertainty associated with the refractive index, as determined through the regression method, is minimal. In the near-IR region, a practically constant value of 7.7×10^{-6} was determined. However, considering the systematic errors of spectroscopic methods and the models used, the overall error is much higher. Based on experience, it can be stated with certainty that the aforementioned errors are significantly higher than the value of 2×10^{-3} reported by

Fig. 3. The spectral dependence of the refractive index n and extinction coefficient k of the TGG crystal determined by the UDM. In the final fit, all of our experimental data, along with tabulated refractive index data determined by Schlarb and Sugg [30], are processed together. The refractive index obtained from an alternative fit, where the tabulated refractive index was omitted from the processed data, is added to the figure for comparison. The extinction coefficients determined for individual TGG samples differ slightly due to varying absorption on localized states; however, these differences are negligible in the refractive index values. The extinction coefficient determined by Jalali et al. [80] is also shown for comparison.

Fig. 4. The same data as in Fig. 3 are shown in detail in the near-IR region. Additionally, the bottom panel shows the absorption coefficient $\alpha = 4\pi k/\lambda$.

Schlarb and Sugg [30] for their method. This is the reason why we consider the final fit is more plausible, as it combines the spectroscopic data obtained on our instruments with the tabulated values of the refractive index.

5.2. Weak absorption in the region of transparency

The extinction coefficient k , describing weak absorption in the transparent region, is depicted in Fig. 3. Absorption in the spectral range of photon energies from 1.4 eV to 3.2 eV, except for the region around 2.54 eV, is primarily determined by scattering processes on localized states, which are modeled independently for each sample. Therefore, slight differences in values for individual samples can be observed.

In the spectral range of photon energies from 0.8 to 1.4 eV, there is no specific source of absorption in the dispersion model. In this spectral

Fig. 5. High-resolution spectral dependencies of the reflectance R and transmittance T measured in the far-IR region ($25\text{--}100\text{ cm}^{-1}$) for thinnest TGG crystal.

range, the weak absorption is determined both by the decay of the Lorentzian components of the TO phonons and partly by the decaying absorption on localized states. Consequently, the accuracy of UDM in this domain is limited, as it is challenging to ascertain the systematic errors associated with transmittance measurements, which are used to derive the values of weak absorption.

In a previous study, Jalali et al. [80] reported an absorption coefficient $\alpha = 4\pi k/\lambda$ of 0.003 cm^{-1} at $\lambda = 1064\text{ nm}$ for a TGG crystal. This value is slightly larger than the one determined from our optical characterization ($0.00175\text{--}0.00186\text{ cm}^{-1}$, see Fig. 4). In private communication with the supplier of sample #1, the authors were informed that the absorption coefficient of their TGG at $\lambda = 1064\text{ nm}$ is 0.0015 cm^{-1} . This value is identical to the one provided by NG Synoptics for their TGG crystals [81]. It can thus be stated that, although it is not feasible to anticipate high precision in determining the absorption coefficient within this spectral range, the value obtained through the presented methodology is in close alignment with the anticipated value.

5.3. Thickness of the TGG samples

In the far-IR spectral region below 0.01 eV , the experimental data for the thinnest sample exhibit interference patterns in both reflectance and transmittance, as illustrated in Fig. 5. The thickness of the thinnest sample was derived from this portion of the experimental data, resulting in a value of $d_{s3} = 0.5240(2)\text{ mm}$. The primary source of uncertainty in determining this thickness is the uncertainty in determining the refractive index in the transparent region, as discussed in the previous paragraph. The refractive index in the far-IR spectral region is then extrapolated from transparent region by a KK consistent model, if the phonon excitations lying between these regions are precisely modeled. Thickness of the other samples are as follows: $d_{s1} = 4.883(2)\text{ mm}$, $d_{s2} = 3.0088(14)\text{ mm}$. These values are determined from the absorption structures in the spectral regions where all three samples are partially transparent (discussed later).

5.4. Surface of the TGG samples

The statistical roughness parameters were derived from the interpretation of optical data and independently by Fourier analysis of the AFM scans, as detailed in Table 3. The surface roughness was modeled by Rayleigh–Rice theory [82,83] in the calculation of optical quantities. A Gaussian autocorrelation function was assumed, in order to determine both the height deviation RMS value σ and the autocorrelation length

Table 3

The roughness parameters (the RMS value of the height deviation σ and the autocorrelation length τ) determined from the fit of optical data and by Fourier analysis of the AFM scans.

Parameter	Sample #1	Sample #2	Sample #3
Optical data			
σ (nm)	2.42(2)	2.26(2)	1.61(3)
τ (nm)	10.9(2)	8.50(15)	7.5(3)
AFM			
σ_H (nm)	0.195(6)	0.739(13)	0.461(5)
τ_H (nm)	37(3)	18.8(5)	14.6(6)
σ_L (nm)	0.124(7)	0.366(8)	0.113(7)
τ_L (nm)	205(17)	209(25)	189(9)

Fig. 6. The AFM scan of TGG crystal #2.

τ . In the case of AFM scan analysis, a two-component roughness was assumed in order to obtain statistical parameters for components with high and low spatial frequencies. The AFM data were processed using the Gwyddion software [84]. For illustration, the AFM scan of sample #2 is shown in Fig. 6.

Although the roughness statistical parameters obtained from optical data do not correspond to those obtained from AFM, the results are not contradictory. It is crucial to take into account the considerable smoothing of AFM data resulting from the finite size of the tip radius. Therefore, the AFM values are considerably underestimated. On the other hand, in the case of optical data, surface effects such as adsorbed layers may lead to the erroneous interpretation of these effects as high-spatial-frequency.

5.5. Phonon absorption

Fig. 7 illustrates the experimental data and the response function in the region of TO phonons. Both reflectance and ellipsometric data of all three samples are practically identical in the spectral range where samples do not transmit light. Furthermore, the values of the pseudodielectric function $\langle \hat{\epsilon} \rangle$, calculated from the measured ellipsometric quantities I_s, I_c, I_n at three incidence angles for all three samples, are also nearly identical to the values of dielectric function $\hat{\epsilon}$, calculated using UDM. This consistency suggests that the surface quality of the samples is sufficient to ensure that it does not influence these optical data. The conversion equations between the associated ellipsometric parameters I_s, I_c, I_n , and the pseudodielectric function $\langle \hat{\epsilon} \rangle$ are given in Appendix D.

Fig. 7. Spectral dependences of near-normal reflectance R , pseudodielectric function $\langle \hat{\epsilon} \rangle = \langle \epsilon_r \rangle + i \langle \epsilon_i \rangle$ and degree of polarization P in the spectral range of TO phonon excitations. Ellipsometric data are measured for all three incidence angles of 55° , 65° and 75° and they are expressed from ellipsometric quantities I_s, I_c, I_n . Values of the dielectric function $\hat{\epsilon} = \epsilon_r + i\epsilon_i$ is calculated using universal dispersion model.

Table 4

Dispersion parameters of TO phonons in the spectral region from 300 to 350 cm^{-1} describing the absorption peak at 312 cm^{-1} (0.0387 eV) and its shoulder at 328 cm^{-1} (0.0407 eV).

$E_{\text{ph},j}$ (cm^{-1})	$N_{\text{ph},j}$ (eV^2)	$M_{\text{ph},j}$ (eV^2)	$B_{\text{ph},j}$ (cm^{-1})	$L_{\text{ph},j}$ ($-$)
311.55	0.00226	-0.00037	6.12	0.51
312.25	0.00330	0.00160	11.72	0.46
324.23	0.00205	0.00171	24.53	0.00
328.50	0.00030	0.00008	9.37	1.00
332.48	0.00066	-0.00393	31.15	1.00

In contrast to the YAG crystal, where each phonon excitation was described by a single asymmetric Voigt peak, it was necessary to use approximately twice as many asymmetric Voigt peaks, *i.e.*, 32, for TGG crystals compared to the number of phonon excitations, *i.e.*, 17 (excluding weak Gaussian peaks that model multi-phonon excitations). In other words, the phonon excitation profiles are significantly more intricate than can be adequately represented by a single asymmetric Voigt peak. We attribute this complexity to the presence of Ga atoms in the crystal lattice existing in two different stable isotopes (^{69}Ga 60.1% and ^{71}Ga 39.9%). These heavier and lighter Ga^{+3} cations are randomly distributed within the crystal lattice, creating a form of disorder that is absent in the YAG crystal.

Even though the difference between the Ga isotope masses is less than 3%, this disorder can be detected by a slightly different peak shape compared to when this disorder is absent in the crystal. For illustration, Table 4 presents the dispersion parameters of the five phonon contributions that describe the asymmetric absorption peak at 312 cm^{-1} and its shoulder at 328 cm^{-1} .

Although the phonon spectrum should have 17 IR-active vibrational modes, only 16 clear absorption peaks were found in the spectrum. In Fig. 8, these modes are labeled with the corresponding wavenumber indicating the peak absorption maximum, as is customary for phonons. The discrepancy may be due to the fact that various vibrational modes are in close proximity to each other, making them indistinguishable in the spectrum. Another possibility is that the undetected vibrational mode is so weak that it was not captured in the experimental data.

5.6. Excitation of f -electrons

The primitive cell of a TGG crystal contains twelve Tb atoms, resulting in a total of 168 localized 4f orbitals in the electronic band structure. These localized orbitals can be observed with small dispersion as partially degenerate horizontal lines (8×12 occupied and 6×12 empty orbitals, see Table 2 and Figs. 14). The ground state corresponds to the f -electron configuration labeled 7F_6 . In this configuration, the upper left index denotes $2S + 1$ (S is total spin number and lower right index J denotes total angular momentum of f -electrons. This means that seven electrons have spin up \uparrow and one electron has spin down \downarrow , *i.e.*, $S = 7 \times 1/2 - 1/2 = 3$ (see Table 2). The total angular momentum is the sum of the angular momentum projections of f -electrons in the given direction plus S . Hence, $J = 3 + S = 6$ because sum of the angular momentum projections of the spin-up electrons is zero and spin-down electron contributed by $+3$. The calculated band structure, obtained using of density functional theory (DFT), is consistent with the aforementioned ground state, 7F_6 .

The lowest excitation energy corresponds to excitations from 7F_6 to 7F_5 states, see Fig. 9. These excitations preserve the total spin, but there is a decrease in the total angular momentum J . It can be understood as excitation of the down spin electron $|\downarrow +3\rangle \rightarrow |\downarrow +2\rangle$. One can expect a very rich spectrum characterized by significant complexity, with numerous peaks, which is due to the splitting of the initial and final states into $2J + 1$ Stark levels. Theoretically, this might be resulting in up to 13×11 absorption peaks. However, not all of these peaks are observed because not all transitions are equally probable, and some levels are indistinguishably close to each other.

In Figs. 10 and 11 the excitations of the 7F_6 to 7F_J states, where $J = 4, 3, 2, 1$, *i.e.*, excitations of the down spin electron $|\downarrow +3\rangle \rightarrow |\downarrow l_z\rangle$, where $l_z = +1, 0, -1, -2$, are depicted. The excitations to the state 7F_0 in the work of Gruber et al. [63] was not identified and studied due to low probability. As illustrated in Fig. 11, discernible, albeit weak, structures are observable within the energy range of 0.73 – 0.75 eV . These structures can be associated with excitations to 7F_0 , although they are approximately 0.04 eV higher in energy than transitions to 7F_1 , which contradicts Gruber et al. who predict a shift of 0.01 eV (80 cm^{-1}).

All excitations of f -electrons that do not change the total spin ($S = 3$, F series) form a continuous broad absorption band with a range from 0.22 to 0.72 eV . Excitation band from 0.25 to 0.31 eV corresponds to the transitions from lowest four Stark levels $Z_{1...4}$ of the 7F_6 ground state to 7F_5 excited state as was identified in [63]. The band width 0.06 eV is associated to Stark splitting $A_{1...9}$ of the 7F_5 state. Transitions from higher Stark levels $Z_{5...13}$ of 7F_6 state with lower energies exhibits reduced transition strength and have not been considered in [63].

The $Z_{1...13}$ Stark level split of 7F_6 state was reported by Gruber et al. [63] at value of 379 cm^{-1} (0.047 eV). Thus, the absorption structures between 0.22 and 0.25 eV in Fig. 9 are postulated correspond to excitations from $Z_{5...13}$ Stark levels. Nevertheless, it is conceivable that these structures may also be subject to influence from multi-phonon excitations. In order to distinguish between electron and

Fig. 8. Transition strength function $F(E) = E\epsilon_i(E)$ in the spectral region of TO phonons.

Fig. 9. Spectral dependences of the transmittances T and transition strength function $F(E) = E\epsilon_i(E)$ of the TGG crystals corresponding to the spectral region of the f-electron excitations from 7F_6 to 7F_5 state.

Fig. 11. Spectral dependences of the transmittances T and transition strength function $F(E) = E\epsilon_i(E)$ of the TGG crystals corresponding to the spectral region of the f-electron excitations from 7F_6 to 7F_2 and 7F_1 states.

Fig. 10. Spectral dependences of the transmittances T and transition strength function $F(E) = E\epsilon_i(E)$ of the TGG crystals corresponding to the spectral region of the f-electron excitations from 7F_6 to 7F_4 and 7F_3 states.

Fig. 12. Spectral dependences of the transmittances T and transition strength function $F(E) = E\epsilon_i(E)$ of the TGG crystals corresponding to the spectral region of the f-electron excitations from 7F_6 to 5D_4 state.

phonon excitations, it would be necessary, for example, to perform measurements at different temperatures or in a magnetic field. In any case, the absorption structures observed at 0.18 eV can be pure phonon excitations.

In addition to excitations of f-electrons, where the total spin S remains unchanged, there are excitations where a change from 3 to 2 occurs. In this case, a single spin-up electron is excited to an empty spin-down state. The excited states are then designated as 5D_4 , 5D_3 , 5G_6 , ${}^5L_{10}$, 5G_5 , 5D_2 , 5G_4 , 5L_9 , etc. [63]. The letters in the designation

Fig. 13. Spectral dependences of the transmittances T and transition strength function $F(E) = E\epsilon_i(E)$ of the TGG crystals corresponding to the spectral region of the f -electron excitations from 7F_6 to 5D_3 , 5G_6 , ${}^5L_{10}$, 5G_5 , 5D_2 , 5G_4 , 5L_9 , etc. states.

of excited states (values of the total orbital momentum L) indicate which spin-up electron was excited in the single-electron scheme. This enables the differentiation of excited states with identical total angular momentum, J , which is indicated in the subscript (see Table 2).

The lowest excitation energy with changing total spin S is observed in the transition from the 7F_6 to 5D_4 state, as illustrated in Fig. 12. These excitations result in the emergence of a weak absorption band that is distinctly positioned within the spectrum around 2.54 eV (488 nm), as can be seen in Fig. 3.

The remaining excitations of f -electrons changing total spin S are situated within the absorption band above 3.2 eV (see Fig. 13). It is not feasible to ascertain the maximum energy associated with these transitions based on transmittance measurements, as they are superimposed by interband transitions of valence electrons associated with extended states. The final discernible absorption structure in the experimental data is observed at 4.1 eV (see Fig. 15).

Calculated electron energy band structures of TGG are shown in Fig. 14. The strongly-correlated f -electrons are inherently difficult to describe properly with DFT calculations [85]. Since the f states are well-localized in general, a local corrections are often used to improve their description. In this regards the onsite hybrid [71] or Hubbard's DFT+ U correction [86] are two popular approaches with computational costs similar to standard DFT. Although the formalism differs somewhat, the two methods yield highly similar results in practice. The Hubbard's correction introduces two empirical parameters, U and J , or effective $U_{\text{eff}} = U - J$ in some simpler formulations which needs to be tuned by hand. Hybrid functional contain a part of exact-exchange, and in fact the exact-exchange fraction can be also understood as a free parameter similarly to the DFT+ U approach. Moreover, as discussed above, while O and Ga atoms are in a non-magnetic configuration, the eight f -electrons of Tb^{3+} give rise to a strong magnetic moment that must be considered. In particular, without spin-polarization, four of the seven two-electron bands will be fully occupied. This is apparent in the calculations presented by Zhang et al. [87], which lead to an inaccurate description, failing to account for the low-energy f transitions observed in the experimental spectra. The orientations and ordering of the magnetic moments (at least at low temperatures) have been reported as quite complex [72,73]; therefore, in this work, we have considered ferromagnetic ordering as the most straightforward step beyond the incorrect non-spin-polarized DFT, while still within the spin-collinear formalism of standard DFT.

If one considers the band structure with plain PBE, *e.g.*, with no onsite hybrid correction, all the f down states are located within the band gap, just directly below the lowest lying empty Ga band with

Table 5

Calculated band structure parameters $E_{f,\text{min}}$, $E_{vc,\text{min}}$ corresponding to the minimum energy between occupied and empty f states and quasiparticle band gap, respectively as dependent on the exact-exchange fraction parameter f_{ee} .

f_{ee} (%)	0	2	5	10	15	20	25
$E_{f,\text{min}}$ (eV)	0	0	0.14	0.37	0.67	1.02	1.37
$E_{vc,\text{min}}$ (eV)	3.36	3.31	3.24	3.26	3.29	3.34	3.34

the total energy width of all the f states below 1 eV. In this case, the f bands remain undivided, suggesting that the material is metallic. The introduction of varying quantities of exact-exchange leads to the formation of a gap between the single occupied and the remaining unoccupied f down bands as well as an increase in the splitting of unoccupied f bands in general. The overall effects are summarized in Table 5. As the exact-exchange fraction increases, the occupied f down band shifts towards the band gap and into the valence region. However, the positions of the first two empty f bands remain mostly constant regardless of the exact-exchange fraction f_{ee} , situated just below the lower empty Ga state, while the higher energy f down bands tend to move into the conduction band with increasing exact-exchange fraction. In this context, the best agreement with the experimental results appears to occur at relatively low hybrid exchange fractions, around 5%, which is surprising given that standard hybrid functionals use much larger fractions around 0.2–0.25 [88–90]. This discrepancy may be attributed to the simplified description of the magnetic state and possibly other approximations, such as the omission of spin-orbit coupling.

5.7. Interband transitions

The valence band of TGG originates from the six occupied p orbitals of the O^{2-} anion, of which there are 48 in the primitive unit cell. In consequence, the valence band is composed of 288 occupied electronic states. The conduction band is formed by the extension of originally unoccupied and released ($\text{Tb } 6s^2$ and $\text{Ga } 4s^2 4p^1$) atomic orbitals.

The lowest experimentally observed excitation with energy 3.99 eV, corresponding to interband transitions, is shown in Fig. 15 (see also $E_{\text{ex},1}$ in Table 6). This excitation energy corresponds to the gap between the bands in the band structure ($E_{vc,\text{min}}$ in Fig. 14), from which, however, the binding energy of the exciton R must be subtracted (see Elliott's model (11)). In the context of our simplified model (13), the parametrization of the binding energy of the excitons was not incorporated. Moreover, within the context of our simplified model, the value of E_g parameter was fitted to the band gap value corresponding

Fig. 14. Electron energy band structure of TGG calculated by DFT using GGA by PBE (left) and using GGA by PBE with onsite hybrid potential with exact-exchange fraction of 0.05 (right). Red and green lines represent spin-down bands, while orange and blue lines represent spin-up bands. The energy of Fermi level was chosen at zero, i. e., $E_F = 0$.

Fig. 15. Spectral dependencies of the transmittance T measured around 4 eV and corresponding modeled transition strength F showing the first and second excitons.

to higher excitations, which exhibit a significantly higher transition strength. Consequently, the E_g value presented in Table 6 does not correspond to the minimum of interband excitations.

The second excitation at energy 4.14 eV does not correspond to an absorption peak; rather, it serves to correct the asymmetry of the first excitation. It is thus imperative to consider both excitations as a unified asymmetry excitation.

In Fig. 16, the second and third excitation structures are shown (they are indexed as 3 and 4). Comparison with *ab initio* calculation suggests that these structures correspond to direct transitions between bands with a minimum in the conduction band at higher energy than that of the first excitation (see Fig. 14). The transition strength of

Table 6

Dispersion parameters describing interband transitions. Energies and broadening parameters are given in eV and transition strengths in eV^2 . In fact, transition strengths were not fitting parameters (see Appendix E).

j	$E_{ex,j}$	$B_{ex,j}$	$N_{Gex,j}$	$N_{Lex,j}$
1	3.9864(2)	0.1030(4)	0.000482	0.000006
2	4.14(10)	0.27(8)	0.000263	0.000004
3	4.7556(4)	0.2225(3)	0.389385	0.000405
4	5.351(2)	0.251(2)	0.542384	53.68665
5	5.802(6)	0.163(3)	1.514191	0.000021
6	5.91(3)	0.570(15)	0.000001	25.75332
7	6.843(3)	0.61(2)	0.000038	7.846791
8	7.448(14)	0.51(4)	4.480194	0.000359
9	8.30(2)	1.4(2)	0.732944	25.54597
10	9.133(16)	1.13(7)	12.34520	17.47547
11	12.6(2)	4.5(12)	0.000359	437.7108
	E_g	E_{bb}	N_{bb}	
	5.6151(15)	12(2)	134.8312	

these excitons is three orders of magnitude higher than that of the first exciton.

Finally, in Fig. 17, additional higher excitations corresponding to structures 5 to 10 are presented, with transition strength exceeding that of the second and third excitons by an order of magnitude. Structure 11 is not included in the spectral range of the experimental data, and thus, the optical constants above 10.3 eV are not very reliable.

Calculated band structures of TGG, with highlighted minimum energy difference for the interband transitions are shown in Fig. 14. However, a known shortcoming of standard DFT (with exchange–correlation effects at the level of local density or generalized gradient approximation) is underestimation of the quasiparticle band gap $E_{vc,min}$, by $\sim 40\%$ on average [91]. As a result, the energies of the unoccupied states in the conduction band are shifted to lower values than experimentally observed. It is also important to note that the energies in question, e.g., the lowest experimentally observed energy of

Fig. 16. Spectral dependencies of the transmittance T and reflectance R measured in the UV range and corresponding modeled transition strength F .

Fig. 17. Spectral dependencies of the reflectance R and associated ellipsometric quantities I_s , I_c , I_n measured in the UV and VUV spectral ranges and corresponding modeled transition strength F . The exciton positions are shown by arrows.

the interband transitions at 3.99 eV, and the lowest energy difference between the occupied state in the valence band and empty state in the conduction bands $E_{vc,min}$, are not directly comparable. In fact, the true quasiparticle band gap $E_{vc,min}$ is greater than 4 eV because the optical transitions are shifted down due to excitonic effects, *i. e.*,

$$E_{ex1} + R_{ex1} = E_{vc,min}, \quad (27)$$

where R_{ex1} is the corresponding exciton binding energy. Nevertheless, while the DFT-calculated band gap is underestimated (unless one opts for a higher step on the Kohn–Sham ladder, like a specifically crafted meta-GGAs, *e. g.*, [92], or full hybrid), the band dispersion of the conduction

bands is usually in a good agreement with results from more advanced methods like hybrids of GW, proved by the fact that good results have been obtained in the past using DFT band structure with a rigid shift of the valence bands, a so-called scissor operator, as a basis for BSE calculations [93]. Thus in practice a DFT groundstate results even using a LDA or GGA can still be helpful in the analysis of optical spectra, assuming one is aware of the various limitations of the methodology.

6. Conclusion

The primary objective of this study was to determine precise optical constants and the appropriate dispersion model that could be applied over a wide spectral range, from 3 meV (25 cm^{-1} , 0.4 mm) to 10.3 eV (83000 cm^{-1} , 120 nm) at the room temperature. The UDM was employed to describe the optical constants of TGG, based upon its successful application in characterizing the optical properties of Si and YAG single crystals. The dispersion parameters of the model were determined by simultaneous interpretation of our spectrophotometric and ellipsometric experimental data along with refractive index data provided by other authors. The weak absorption was determined across the entire transparency region, offering valuable insights into the potential use of TGG in high-power lasers with different fundamental emission wavelengths.

Considerable attention was dedicated to the optical properties in the near-IR region, where these crystals are used as Faraday isolators. In this spectral range, fluctuations in weak absorption were observed depending on the crystal supplier. These fluctuations are likely influenced by the density of imperfections in the crystal lattice. These optical constants or the dispersion model, where some parameters are fitted, can subsequently be employed to design and optimize layered systems (*e. g.*, AR coatings) on TGG crystals, wherein the crystal will serve as an optically active element.

A secondary outcome of our investigation is an enhanced comprehension of the absorption processes occurring in the optical crystals. The implementation of an accurate modeling of phonon excitations facilitated an enhanced comprehension of the underlying physical principles governing the absorption profile of phonon peaks. It was discovered that TGG exhibits a much more complex absorption profile of TO phonons compared to the YAG crystal, which has the same crystal structure but with terbium and gallium atoms in place of the yttrium and aluminum ones. The more complex absorption profile of TGG can be attributed to the natural occurrence of gallium isotopes in a 3:2 ratio, ^{69}Ga and ^{71}Ga , which have different masses.

Using the precise measurement of the optical properties in the vicinity of the fundamental absorption edge, we were able to demonstrate the excitonic nature of the interband transitions at 3.99 eV. This exciton was observed to be markedly weaker, with transition strength three orders of magnitude lower than the next excitons observed at 4.76 and 5.35 eV.

Three weak absorption bands in mid-IR, visible and UV range, representing the excitation of f-electrons, were studied in high resolution with an emphasis on the accuracy of the optical constants.

The overall qualitative interpretation of electronic excitations was conducted out using *ab initio* calculations of the electronic band structure. In this interpretation, it was discussed why these calculations cannot be quantitatively compared with optical measurements, a common but incorrect practice. The reason for this discrepancy is the inherent limitations of ground state calculations using DFT, particularly the lack of inclusion of excitonic effects within these calculations.

In this study, only the optical properties at room temperature were examined. However, further investigation could be conducted at low temperatures and/or the magneto-optical properties of TGG crystals could be examined in the future.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Daniel Franta: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Mihai-George Mureşan:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Pavel Ondračka:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Beáta Hroncová:** Writing – review & editing, Software. **František Viřďa:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

This article was developed with the support of AI-assisted language enhancement technology. The technology was used to refine the English language and rectify grammatical errors. The authors ensured the accuracy and relevance of the content.

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Appendix A. Broadband contribution

Normalized transition strength function of broad band contribution is calculated as follows:

$$F_{\text{bb}}^0(E) = \frac{F(E)}{C_{\text{Nbb}}}, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where

$$F(E) = \frac{(|E| - E_g)^2 \Theta(|E| - E_g)}{[(|E| - E_g)^2 + E_q^2] E^2}, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$E_q = \sqrt{\frac{(E_{\text{bb}} - E_g)^3}{E_g}}, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$C_{\text{Nbb}} = \int_0^\infty F(E) dE = A \ln \frac{E_q}{E_g} + B + \frac{\pi}{2} K, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$A = \frac{-2E_g E_q^2}{(E_g^2 + E_q^2)^2}, \quad B = \frac{E_g}{E_g^2 + E_q^2}, \quad K = \frac{-E_q(E_g^2 - E_q^2)}{(E_g^2 + E_q^2)^2}. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

The real and imaginary part of the response function is calculated from normalized transition strength function using Kramers–Kronig integral and using definition as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_{r,\text{bb}}(E) &= N_{\text{bb}} \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{F_{\text{bb}}^0(X)}{X^2 - E^2} dX \\ &= \frac{N_{\text{bb}}}{C_{\text{Nbb}}} \frac{2}{\pi} \left(\frac{A \ln E_g - B}{E^2} - C(E) \ln |E_g - E| \right. \\ &\quad \left. - D(E) \ln |E_g + E| - L(E) \ln E_q + \frac{\pi}{2} G(E) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$C(E) = \frac{(E_g - E)^2}{2[(E_g - E)^2 + E_q^2] E^3}, \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$D(E) = \frac{-(E_g + E)^2}{2[(E_g + E)^2 + E_q^2] E^3}, \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$L(E) = \frac{2E_q^2(2E_g^3 - 2E_g E_q^2 - E_g E^2)}{H(E)}, \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$G(E) = \frac{E_q[(E_g^2 - E_q^2) E^2 + 6E_g^2 E_q^2 - E_g^4 - E_q^4]}{H(E)}, \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$\begin{aligned} H(E) &= E_q^8 + 2E_q^6(2E_g^2 + E^2) + E_q^4(6E_g^4 + 2E_g^2 E^2 + E^4) \\ &\quad + 2E_g^2 E_q^2(2E_g^4 - E_g^2 E^2 + E^4) + E_g^4(E_g^2 - E^2)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.11})$$

and

$$\chi_{i,\text{bb}}(E) = \frac{N_{\text{bb}}}{E} F_{\text{bb}}^0(E). \quad (\text{A.12})$$

Appendix B. Exponential tail

The normalized transition strength function of the exponential tail model can be written as follows

$$F_{\text{et}}^0(E) = F_e^0(E) \Theta(E_g - |E|) + F_r^0(E) \Theta(|E| - E_g), \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where $F_e^0(E)$ and $F_r^0(E)$ are defined in (22) and (23). The normalization constants and internal parameter E_x are calculated as

$$A_e = \frac{3U}{D}, \quad A_r = \frac{3E_g^2 V^2}{D}, \quad E_x = \frac{E_g(V - U)}{V}, \quad (\text{B.2})$$

where

$$D = 3E_u U \left[\sinh\left(\frac{E_g}{E_u}\right) - \frac{E_g}{E_u} \right] + E_g (U^2 + UV + V^2), \quad (\text{B.3})$$

$$U = \cosh\left(\frac{E_g}{E_u}\right) - 1, \quad V = 2U + \frac{E_g}{2E_u} \sinh\left(\frac{E_g}{E_u}\right). \quad (\text{B.4})$$

The real part of response function is calculated using the Kramers–Kronig relations, *i. e.*,

$$\chi_{r,\text{et}}(E) = N_{\text{et}} \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{F_{\text{et}}^0(X)}{X^2 - E^2} dX. \quad (\text{B.5})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_{r,\text{et}}(E) &= \frac{2N_{\text{et}}}{\pi} \left\{ \frac{A_e}{4E} \left[\exp\left(\frac{E_g}{E_u}\right) \left(\tilde{E}_i\left(\frac{E_g - E}{E_u}\right) - \tilde{E}_i\left(\frac{E_g + E}{E_u}\right) \right) \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. + \exp\left(-\frac{E_g}{E_u}\right) \left(\tilde{E}_i\left(-\frac{E_g - E}{E_u}\right) - \tilde{E}_i\left(-\frac{E_g + E}{E_u}\right) \right) \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. - 2 \ln \left| \frac{E_g - E}{E_g + E} \right| \right] \\ &\quad + \frac{A_r}{E^4} \left[E_x \ln \left| 1 - \frac{E^2}{E_g^2} \right| - \frac{E_x^2 + E^2}{2E} \ln \left| \frac{E_g - E}{E_g + E} \right| \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{E_x^2 + E^2}{E_g} + \frac{E_x E^2}{E_g^2} - \frac{E_x^2 E^2}{3E_g^3} \right] \left. \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

Fig. C.1. The spectral dependence of the refractive index n of the TGG crystal determined by the UDM was compared with tabulated data obtained from various sources in the literature [30,77–79]. In the final fit, all of our experimental data along with tabulated refractive index data determined by Schlarb and Sugg [30] are modeled and processed all together. The TGG refractive index obtained from a fit of all experimental data except the tabulated refractive index data is shown for comparison in Fig. C.1.

where special function $\tilde{E}_i(\cdot)$ is scaled exponential integral [33]:

$$\tilde{E}_i(x) = \exp(-x) \int_{-\infty}^x \frac{\exp(t)}{t} dt. \quad (\text{B.7})$$

The imaginary part of the contribution to the dielectric function (susceptibility) is calculated from definition

$$\chi_{i,\text{et}}(E) = \frac{N_{\text{et}}}{E} F_{\text{et}}^0(E). \quad (\text{B.8})$$

Appendix C. Refractive index of TGG

This appendix will discuss the independent refractive indices of TGG found in the literature.

The first set of tabulated data presented in Fig. C.1 represents two refractive indices determined from prisms of TGG single crystals using a “modified” MDM methodology by Dentz et al. [77]. The authors did not state the estimated measurement error nor specify which particular MDM modification was involved in the measurement. As can be observed, the tabulated refractive indices exhibit less dispersion than the refractive index determined in this work using spectroscopic methods and fitted with the UDM model. Although spectroscopic methods do not offer high accuracy in determining the absolute value of the refractive index, the determination of dispersion in the transparent region is relatively accurate. This is the main reason for our doubts regarding the presented data, despite it being determined using a highly accurate MDM method.

Tien et al. [78] demonstrated that the refractive indices in the near-IR region for all types of gallium garnet crystals are very similar, specifically 1.94(2) at 1523 nm. However, the authors did not disclose the method or sources used to obtain the refractive indices. The aforementioned interval has been included in Fig. C.1, albeit not as a TGG refractive index, but rather due to the absence of alternative sources.

The most reliable tabulated data appear to be the refractive indices published by Schlarb and Sugg [30]. In their work, the authors used an interferometric method suitable for determining the refractive index of

plane-parallel plates, achieving an accuracy of up to 2×10^{-4} [94,95]. For TGG, they reported a lower accuracy, *i. e.*, 2×10^{-3} [30], but still much greater than what can be achieved through spectrometric methods. Variable angle spectroscopic ellipsometry and spectrophotometric methods are subject to large systematic errors that cannot be eliminated. In the case of spectrophotometric methods employing reference measurements on a normal or empty channel, the measured values of reflectance and transmittance cannot be relied upon as absolute values. In the case of ellipsometry, it is crucial to account for the non-ideality of the sample surface, which will inevitably exhibit some degree of roughness and transition layers. Even in the ideal case of an atomically smooth surface, the response function does not exhibit a step-like behavior due to the influence of surface effects.

To enhance the precision of the refractive index modeled using UDM, we incorporated the tabulated data from [30] into our heterogeneous data set. As illustrated in Fig. C.1, the refractive index exhibits a slight decrease in value when the tabulated data is excluded, which aligns with the systematic error observed in our spectroscopic data. It is important to emphasize that even in this case, the uncertainty of the absolute values of the spectroscopic quantities and the non-ideality of the crystal surface (roughness) have been taken into account. Furthermore, the refractive indices published by Villora et al. [79] also appear to be exemplary tabulated data. To determine the refractive index, the authors employed a total reflection technique between a known glass and a TGG crystal. Using this method, they obtained refractive indices at four wavelengths. However, they presented the results using the following physically incorrect dispersion formula

$$n^2 = A + \frac{B}{\lambda^2 - C} - D\lambda^2 \quad (\text{C.1})$$

with the following dispersion parameters $A = 3.73895$, $B = 0.0516156 \mu\text{m}^2$, $C = -0.00115321 \mu\text{m}^2$ and $D = 0.00590524 \mu\text{m}^{-2}$, and using wavelength values, *i. e.*, 440, 638, 1064 and 1545 nm.

The four refractive indices measured by Villora et al. [79] can be reconstructed using four-parametric formula (C.1) as 2.00071, 1.96607,

1.94366, and 1.93558. However, it is inadvisable to employ this physically incorrect formula for interpolation or extrapolation of data outside the specified wavelengths. The authors presented the dispersion formula (C.1) as the Sellmeier formula, which is an inaccurate representation because the multi-term Sellmeier formula is expressed as follows [96]:

$$n^2 = 1 + \sum_k \frac{A_k \lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_k^2}, \quad (\text{C.2})$$

or in an equivalent form. Regarding the dispersion parameters, it is imperative that the pole positions λ_j must be represented as real numbers (causality is violated in the case of complex values). Furthermore, the forces A_j must be positive real values in accordance with the principles of thermodynamic equilibrium of the system. Negative values of A_j indicate a negative density of charged particles or an inverse electron population in the case of non-equilibrium systems (dielectrically active medium in the laser).

The first and third terms of formula (C.1) are acceptable because they correspond to the cases when $\lambda \gg \lambda_j$ and $\lambda \ll \lambda_j$. However, the second term is physically problematic, especially when the value of C is negative. In this case, the second term violates causality and conformity with summation rules.

The reconstructed refractive indices can be fitted using the two-term Sellmeier formula with the following three parameters: $A_1 = 2.749(4)$, $\lambda_1 = 128.3(13)$ nm and $B_2 = A_2/\lambda_2^2 = 9(2) \times 10^{-9}$ nm⁻², as λ_2 is too large and correlated with A_2 for accurate fitting, *i. e.*,

$$n^2 \approx 1 + \frac{A_1 \lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_1^2} - B_2 \lambda^2. \quad (\text{C.3})$$

In this context, the two terms represent the average contributions of electron and phonon excitations, respectively. It can thus be assumed that this approximation of Sellmeier formula (C.3) is superior to the physically incorrect (C.1) in interpolating and extrapolating values. Despite the lack of a perfect match between the modeled and experimental data (RMS of residuals is 0.00057), this approximation shows greater effectiveness in extrapolating values. As shown in Fig. C.1, the different formulas exhibit significant deviations in the extrapolated region below the lowest wavelength of 440 nm. It is evident that interpolation between experimental points achieves good accuracy for the given rendering. The single-term Sellmeier formula produces comparable practically useful results with a marginally inferior fit: $A_1 = 2.732(5)$ and $\lambda_1 = 132.7(22)$ nm (RMS of residuals is 0.00182).

Furthermore, the data obtained by Schlarb and Sugg can be fitted using both single-term and two-term Sellmeier formulas. In the case the two parameter single-term Sellmeier formula the following values of parameters were found: $A_1 = 2.7334(8)$ and $\lambda_1 = 134.4(3)$ nm (RMS of residuals is 0.00039). The λ_1 value corresponds to the mean electron excitation energy in the harmonic oscillator model [25]

$$E_{\text{el}} = \frac{C_{E\lambda}}{\lambda_1} = 9.225 \text{ eV},$$

where $C_{E\lambda} = hc10^9/e = 1239.841984$ is the conversion constant between nm and eV units, and the dimensionless amplitude A_1 represents the effective transition strength

$$N_{\text{el}} = \frac{\pi C_{E\lambda}^2 A_1}{2\lambda_1^2} = 365.39 \text{ eV}^2.$$

The low RMS residual suggests that the refractive index measurement error might be lower than reported by the authors. Therefore, it can be concluded that the error is likely random. However, the two-term Sellmeier formula yielded unphysical results: $A_1 = 2.732(3)$, $\lambda_1 = 134.7(8)$ nm and $B_2 = -1.0(25) \times 10^{-9}$ nm⁻², indicating a negative phonon contribution. Considering the uncertainty in the B_2 parameter, it is apparent that the data reported by Schlarb and Sugg were obtained at frequencies where the phonon contribution cannot be accurately determined.

Appendix D. Convention of ellipsometric quantities

The Mueller matrix of reflected light from an isotropic system can be expressed using the reflectance R and the normalized Mueller matrix (NMM) as follows [29,97]

$$\mathbf{M} = R \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -I_n & 0 & 0 \\ -I_n & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & I_c & I_s \\ 0 & 0 & -I_s & I_c \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{D.1})$$

where I_s, I_c, I_n are three independent components, commonly referred to as associated ellipsometric parameters. In the context of ellipsometry of isotropic systems, three other quantities are often used to describe the NMM:

classical ellipsometric angles Ψ, Δ, P

$$I_s = P \sin 2\Psi \sin \Delta, \quad (\text{D.2})$$

$$I_c = P \sin 2\Psi \cos \Delta, \quad (\text{D.3})$$

$$I_n = P \cos 2\Psi, \quad (\text{D.4})$$

where Ψ, Δ and P are azimuth, phase change and degree of polarization, respectively. The quantity P represents the degree of polarization of the reflected light, assuming elliptically polarized light with equal p and s amplitude is incident on the measured system. In Woollam ellipsometers, the depolarization factor D is used instead of P :

$$P = \sqrt{I_s^2 + I_c^2 + I_n^2} = \sqrt{1 - D}. \quad (\text{D.5})$$

ellipsometric ratio $\hat{\rho}, P$

$$\hat{\rho} = \frac{I_c + iI_s}{P - I_n}. \quad (\text{D.6})$$

For non-depolarizing systems, $P = 1$ holds:

$$\hat{\rho} = \tan \Psi \exp(i\Delta) = \frac{\hat{r}_p}{\hat{r}_s}, \quad (\text{D.7})$$

where \hat{r}_p and \hat{r}_s are the complex Fresnel reflection coefficients.

pseudodielectric function $\langle \hat{\epsilon} \rangle, P$

$$\langle \hat{\epsilon} \rangle = n_0^2 \sin^2 \theta_0 \left[1 + \left(\frac{1 - \hat{\rho}}{1 + \hat{\rho}} \right)^2 \tan^2 \theta_0 \right], \quad (\text{D.8})$$

where n_0 and θ_0 are refractive index of ambient (usually $n_0 = 1$) and angle of incidence, respectively.

It is important to emphasize that the quantities $\Psi, \Delta, \hat{\rho}$ and $\langle \hat{\epsilon} \rangle$ are ambiguously defined in practice for depolarizing systems, *i. e.*, when $P < 1$. For example, the Woollam IR-VASE ellipsometer model uses the standard definitions (D.2)–(D.4). The Woollam V-VASE ellipsometer model, however, uses the following definitions for Ψ and Δ :

$$I_s = Y \sin 2\Psi \sin \Delta, \quad (\text{D.9})$$

$$I_c = Y \sin 2\Psi \cos \Delta, \quad (\text{D.10})$$

$$I_n = \cos 2\Psi, \quad (\text{D.11})$$

where

$$Y = \frac{\sqrt{1 - D - \cos^2 2\Psi}}{\sin 2\Psi}. \quad (\text{D.12})$$

However, the depolarization factor corresponds to the standard definition (D.5).

Appendix E. Total transition strength of excitations of valence electrons

The transition strengths of the individual parts of the interband transition model are parameterized using the total transition strength N_{vc} and the relative strength parameters $A_{ex,j}$ and $G_{ex,j}$ as follows:

$$N_{Gex,j} = \frac{N_{vc} A_{ex,j} G_{ex,j}}{1 + \sum_{k=1}^{11} A_{ex,k}}, \quad (E.1)$$

$$N_{Lex,j} = \frac{N_{vc} A_{ex,j} (1 - G_{ex,j})}{1 + \sum_{k=1}^{11} A_{ex,k}}, \quad (E.2)$$

$$N_{bb} = \frac{N_{vc}}{1 + \sum_{k=1}^{11} A_{ex,k}}. \quad (E.3)$$

Due to the uncertainty in the transition strength distribution for energies higher than the maximum photon energy used in VUV spectrophotometry (10.3 eV), the total transition strength is determined with a large relative error:

$$N_{vc} = 723(59) \text{ eV}^2.$$

However, this large uncertainty in determining the transition strength of valence electrons does not significantly affect the uncertainty in determining the optical constants in the region where the experimental data are measured.

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